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The non violent Communication

The different situations that affect our lives might have an impact in others' lives and when that happens we tend to forget because that is what we have been taught to do along the years, although we make many mistakes which can damage other that is how life is supposed to be for most of us. At the end of the day, we fall into the game of Who is right? A game where everybody loses and that helps to create conflicts between the people.

If you are wrong, you deserve to suffer or at least that is what humans are taught. We know that if we do something wrong then we must pay for it and that usually involves receiving the same pain or more if possible that we have created on others. No matters if it is a punishment given by a judge or a moral watched in a cartoon, the heroes always punish the bad ones by using violence.

As a hero, you are right, therefore you get a reward and that tells us that if we are good with each other we need a prize because it is not common, as if it was something hard to achieve. For communication and any other relation, we should have a process that guides us in the good and bad situation, and also being compassionate to the others and ourselves.

Rosenberg (2005) talks about the process for avoiding violence in classes, he stated that first, we observe what is actually happening in a situation: what are we observing others saying or doing that is either enriching or not enriching our life? The trick is to be able to articulate this observation without introducing any judgment or evaluation—to simply say what people are doing that we either like or don't like.

In the same way, Rosenberg also added that we state how we feel when we observe this action: are we hurt, scared, joyful, amused, irritated, etc.? And thirdly, we say what needs of ours are connected to the feelings we have identified. An awareness of these three components is present when we use NVC to clearly and honestly express how we are. Finally, the immediate request, in this fourth component addresses what we are wanting from the other person that would enrich our lives or make life more wonderful for us.

In education, depending of the type of population we are working with following a process helps us connect with each other and ourselves in a way that is easy for everyone to understand the concerns we might have and what is exactly what we expect from them. Especially when working with people who are learning a foreign language that can be very useful. The ethics are clear on guiding us according to what we think is right or wrong, but the communication is what we are observing, feeling, and needing and what we are requesting to facilitate the process and avoiding unethical issues that might come during the learning and teaching environment.

Reference:

Rosenberg, M (2005). Nonviolent communication : a language of life / by Marshall B. Rosenberg. -- 2nd ed. Retrieved from https://ulatinaonline.com/pluginfile.php/423761/mod_resource/content/2/Nonviolent%20Communication%20by%20Marshall%20Rosenberg.pdf